

PSYCHOLOGY

MANIFESTATION EMOTIONAL BURNOUT SYNDROME IN THE PEDAGOGICAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

The rapid socio-economic changes of the modern era and the increasing psychological burden in the work environment have led to the widespread occurrence of emotional burnout syndrome among teachers. Emotional burnout is a complex psychological process that occurs as a result of prolonged stress and professional demands gradually depleting the internal resources of the individual. The syndrome manifests itself in three main components: emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and a decrease in the sense of personal achievement. Emotional exhaustion is characterized by a decrease in energy and motivation, depersonalization by distance and indifference in social relationships, and a decrease in the sense of personal achievement by a weakening of belief in the value of activity.

Symptoms of emotional burnout manifest themselves at the physiological, psychological and behavioral levels. Physiological signs include chronic fatigue, sleep disturbances and weakened immunity. Psychological symptoms include apathy, anxiety and attention problems. At the behavioral level, there is a decrease in work performance, social isolation and avoidance of communication.

Burnout develops in stages: from an initial stage of enthusiasm to stages of stagnation and apathy. This process is deepened by the interaction of individual, social and organizational factors. Social factors include societal expectations and workload, psychological factors include perfectionism and stress management, and organizational factors include peer support and the quality of the work environment.

Individual and organizational measures are necessary to prevent emotional burnout. Individual strategies include stress management and motivation enhancement, while social interventions include social support and collaboration with colleagues. Organizational approaches include workload optimization and strengthening psychological services.

Consequently, burnout has a serious impact on teachers' professional performance and psychological well-being. It is important to implement both individual and organizational measures to prevent it.

Keywords: emotional burnout, occupational stress, depersonalization, sense of personal accomplishment, Maslach model, preventive measures.

Introduction

The rapid socio-economic changes of the modern era, the increase in psychological burden in professions that require close contact with people, and the uncertainty in the work environment have led to the widespread spread of emotional burnout syndrome. Emotional burnout syndrome was first used by H.J. Freudenberger in 1974, and later put into a scientific framework by Maslach and Jackson.

The emotional intensity of pedagogical activity, constant communication, high social responsibility and evaluation pressure put teachers at risk of emotional burnout. In this regard, it is of particular importance to investigate the nature, symptoms, stages and prevention of the syndrome.

Emotional burnout is a psychological syndrome characterized by exhaustion, indifference to activity, emotional detachment from interpersonal relationships, and decreased efficiency of professional activity as a result of prolonged emotional, intellectual, and social overload. To understand the essence of burnout, it is important to consider it not only as an emotional state, but also as the result of a whole range of neurophysiological and socio-psychological processes.

In psychological literature, emotional burnout is explained as an adaptation disorder resulting from the gradual depletion of internal psychological resources

by the constant demands faced by a person during his professional activity. This process usually develops slowly, in stages, and a person often realizes that he has fallen into a state of exhaustion too late, because the initial symptoms of the syndrome begin with a loss of motivation, emotional fluctuations, and psychological fatigue.

The essence of emotional burnout is also related to the mutual imbalance of emotions, motivation and personal value systems. When there is a mismatch between the demands of professional activity and the psychological and physiological capabilities of a person, a person begins to feel increasingly powerless and ineffective. At this time, emotional energy decreases, communication becomes difficult, negative emotions towards work are formed, and a person shows a distant, sometimes cold attitude towards his professional role.

Modern approaches consider emotional burnout not only as a result of individual characteristics, but also as a product of interaction with the work environment, social relations, organizational structure and expectations of society. That is, the syndrome arises as a result of a combination of both personal, organizational and social factors. Depending on the profession, the forms of manifestation of burnout may vary, especially in the social sphere - in professions that are in close

contact with people, such as teaching, medicine, psychology, social service, management, emotional burnout is observed at a higher level.

The level of emotional burnout can also be linked to Hans Selye's "general adaptation syndrome", which studies the body's response mechanisms to stress and deals with physiological reactions and changes occurring in the body. "According to Selye, it has 3 phases: 1) general danger and warning phase - the excitement phase; 2) resistance phase; 3) shock phase" [4, p.6]. "H. Selye called stress a non-specific defense reaction against any extraordinary impact" [3, p.346].

Emotional burnout syndrome, unlike ordinary fatigue or ordinary work stress, is a long-term and systemic multifaceted psychological process that negatively affects a person's personal well-being, professional productivity, social relationships, and overall psychological health. A proper understanding of its essence allows for the effective organization of both diagnostics and preventive and corrective measures.

To fully understand the psychological nature of burnout syndrome, the three-component structure proposed by Christina Maslach and her colleagues is considered the main theoretical framework. According to this model, burnout is not just an expression of general fatigue, but a complex psychological phenomenon consisting of systemic changes that occur in three main areas of a person's emotional, social and professional functioning. Below is a detailed explanation of each component:

Emotional exhaustion - is the main component characterized by the fact that a person exhausts his emotional energy against the background of prolonged tension, emotional overload and high responsibility. At this stage, a person feels chronically tired, "psychologically exhausted", emotionally weak and vulnerable. Emotional exhaustion is more related to the reduction and depletion of internal psychological resources. Thus, a person has difficulty responding emotionally as before, has difficulty finding motivation for himself, and his tolerance to stress is sharply weakened.

Clinical manifestations of this component can manifest themselves in the form of sleep disorders, a constant feeling of physical fatigue, headaches, psychosomatic reactions, a decrease in overall energy levels, and emotional fluctuations. In the professional field, emotional exhaustion results in a decrease in the quality of work, a slowdown in the decision-making process, and a loss of attention. In this sense, emotional exhaustion is considered the initial and most critical indicator of the syndrome.

Depersonalization - is characterized by maintaining emotional distance from people with whom a person interacts in their professional activities, treating them as objects, and forming an indifferent attitude. This component is especially pronounced in people working in "person-to-person" professional fields. For professionals such as teachers, psychologists, doctors, and social workers, depersonalization can also play the role of an emotional defense mechanism. That is, a person maintains distance in relationships to protect themselves from further burdening.

In the depersonalization stage, a person has difficulty showing empathy towards others, develops intolerance towards communication, and sometimes even develops negative and sarcastic attitudes. There is apathy towards professional activity, a decrease in faith in the meaning of work, and a cooling of relations with colleagues and students. This both creates a tendency to conflict in the work environment and sharply reduces the quality of interpersonal relationships.

Decreased sense of personal accomplishment - It is characterized by a person's undervaluation of their professional achievements, seeing themselves as incompetent, less productive, and less influential. In this case, the person is unable to objectively evaluate their work results, belittles their achievements, and their professional self-confidence is significantly weakened.

A decrease in the sense of personal achievement leads to both a weakening of professional motivation and a loss of self-confidence. These changes are usually accompanied by a decrease in performance, a decrease in initiative, a fading interest in new ideas, and a weakening attitude towards the learning process. This situation manifests itself in teachers as a decrease in interest in applying new approaches to the lesson, a weakening of motivation for personal professional development, and a devaluation of the results of their own activities.

Maslach's three-component model is the most widely used scientific framework for both diagnostic and corrective treatment of burnout. This structure:

- allows you to determine at what level and in which area the burn is most pronounced;
- enables targeted planning of corrective and preventive measures;
- serves as the main theoretical basis for explaining the interrelationships between emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and a decreased sense of personal accomplishment;
- It is a valid model for studying specific manifestations of burnout in professional fields.

This model also forms the basis of an internationally accepted diagnostic tool (emotional exhaustion assessment) such as the **Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI)**. Therefore, the assessment of emotional burnout in research, organizational psychology, and psychological assistance is almost always based on this tripartite structure [1, p.146].

Since emotional burnout syndrome is a multidimensional psychological phenomenon, its effects are not limited to the emotional sphere. It causes disturbances in the physiological, psychological and behavioral systems of a person that interact with each other. These manifestations allow us to determine the depth and stage of burnout and are especially clearly observed in professional groups that carry a high stress load, such as teachers.

Physical symptoms. According to Freudenberger and Richelson, people experiencing burnout are generally talented, confident, energetic, enthusiastic about their work, working overtime, and achieving high performance despite insomnia in their early years. Over time, for various reasons, these individuals' metabolisms begin to malfunction, sapping their energy. The depletion of energy individuals project onto their work

and their surroundings can lead to serious physical problems. Burnout initially manifests itself as mild symptoms. These include fatigue and exhaustion, headaches, lethargy, and sleep disturbances. If precautions are not taken, persistent colds, decreased resistance to infections, weight loss or obesity, difficulty breathing, general aches and pains, gastrointestinal disorders, high blood pressure, high cholesterol, muscle tension, heart palpitations, and skin conditions can develop. If these and similar conditions persist, individuals should not ignore these symptoms and should take preventative measures promptly. These symptoms can be a sign of burnout.

Psychological symptoms. "Psychological symptoms are less pronounced than other symptoms that can be observed in individuals experiencing burnout. These symptoms include feelings of frustration and irritability, vulnerability to psychological injury and psychological problems, unexplained restlessness and anxiety, impatience, decreased self-confidence, hostility toward the environment, powerlessness, loss of energy, hopelessness related to work, criticism of others, apathy, increased family problems, dissatisfaction, the development of negative attitudes toward life, a decrease in positive emotions such as kindness, respect, and friendship, uncertainty and confusion in thoughts, unfounded suspicions and paranoia, depression, feelings of guilt, and helplessness. Psychological symptoms of burnout also manifest as thoughts of quitting work and frequent reluctance to go to work. When these symptoms occur, an individual's sense of accomplishment is damaged. When an individual's self-confidence and appreciation for accomplishment diminish, the groundwork for other burnout symptoms is laid, and recovery from this state becomes much more difficult. Because the individual believes wholeheartedly that he is unsuccessful and useless due to the feelings of disappointment, frustration and guilt he experiences" [2, p.30-31].

Behavioral symptoms. Behavioral symptoms of burnout are more easily observed by others than physical and psychological symptoms. These symptoms can manifest as general reactions such as forgetfulness, feelings of failure, family conflicts, decreased concentration, irritability, sudden outbursts, frequent crying spells, a desire for solitude, resentment, and feelings of being unappreciated. Some work-specific symptoms can also be considered. These include: slowing down work, tendencies to steal, disengagement, deterioration in the quality of service, inappropriate interventions against clients and an increase in complaints from clients, document fraud, poor job performance, cynicism and accusation toward colleagues, job dissatisfaction, a tendency to seek new professional training, late arrivals and absences, decreased organizational commitment, increased turnover, increased absences and late arrivals due to illness, and a desire to leave the job and transfer to other job positions. Due to such symptoms, individuals who can't find peace of mind, find no pleasure in anything they do, struggle to maintain their work, and habitually jump from one task to another, often focusing on other things to forget their problems. These include overeating, consuming so much tea and coffee that it threatens their health, and consuming alcohol to

the point of becoming an alcoholic. Furthermore, insomnia can cause significant distress, and to reduce the tension, individuals may resort to tranquilizers and narcotics. All of these factors exacerbate health problems and reduce work productivity. If burnout symptoms aren't recognized and addressed promptly, they can worsen. Initially presenting as headaches, decreased self-confidence, and irritability, they can eventually develop into more harmful and destructive symptoms, sometimes even resulting in suicide.

Emotional burnout syndrome is not a sudden process. This process is formed gradually and is characterized by the gradual depletion of a person's psychological, emotional and behavioral resources. Although there are various stage divisions in the literature, in the context of pedagogical activity, a classical model consisting of four stages is most often applied: enthusiasm, stagnation, frustration and apathy. These stages are closely related to the dynamics of teacher activity, the intensity of emotional load and the level of stress in the professional environment.

The stage of enthusiasm and excitement. The initial stage of the burnout process is usually characterized as a period of high motivation and strong ideals. This stage is especially observed in teachers who are just starting their profession, as well as in specialists who are starting work with a new position or class. During this period, a person feels high energy and strong internal enthusiasm; devotes himself completely to work, sometimes putting personal needs on the back burner; strives for perfection in his activities, tries to build a flawless and exemplary work model; forms very high expectations of both himself and the profession and has difficulty assessing the correspondence of these expectations to reality.

While this situation may seem positive at first glance, it is precisely this excessive idealism and excessive use of resources that creates the basis for burnout in later stages. As the teacher acts without considering the long-term consequences of the energy he or she expends during this period, his or her emotional balance begins to deteriorate, but he or she does not yet realize it.

Stagnation stage. After the enthusiasm stage, the first decline in motivation occurs as the individual faces the challenges of real work conditions. In the stagnation stage, the gradual depletion of energy and emotional resources begins; the previous enthusiasm for work weakens; it becomes clear that high expectations do not coincide with the real work reality; the individual's motivation level decreases, and the previous meaning of professional activity begins to be undermined.

In teachers, this stage is usually accompanied by an increase in teaching workload, difficulties in classroom management, communication problems with students, parents and colleagues, and the additional stress of the assessment process. The person feels the initial signs of emotional exhaustion, but may normalize it and not pay much attention to it due to the normalization of the situation.

Frustration stage. The frustration stage is a deeper and more severe period of the burnout process. At this stage, the feeling of dissatisfaction with work

intensifies, the person is not satisfied with his or her activity; emotional exhaustion manifests itself more prominently, energy reserves are significantly reduced; the person begins to feel unsuccessful, ineffective and burdened; negative emotions towards the teaching profession - irritation, resentment, distrust and even aggression - can form.

At this stage, symptoms of depersonalization become more apparent. The teacher's relationships with students and colleagues are characterized by a weakening of emotional attachment, a distant and cold attitude, a decrease in empathy, and a more formal nature of the teaching process. As the person feels that he or she is not achieving his or her ideals, internal tension increases, which accelerates emotional burnout.

Apathy stage. Apathy is considered the last and most severe stage of emotional burnout. At this stage, the person falls into a state characterized by complete emotional detachment and indifference; previous interest in work is completely extinguished, motivation drops to a minimum level; social isolation increases, communication with colleagues and students is limited; only minimal energy is spent on professional activity; the sense of personal achievement is completely weakened and the person considers himself worthless.

The apathy stage, if not intervened, can pose serious risks to the teacher's psychological health. This situation can sometimes lead to depressive disorders, the development of psychosomatic diseases, and long-term occupational stress. As the stage progresses, the likelihood of the teacher withdrawing from the profession, quitting work, or experiencing severe emotional disturbances increases.

The formation of emotional burnout syndrome in teachers is a multifactorial process and arises as a result of the interaction of social, psychological and socio-psychological factors. These factors are determined not only by the individual characteristics of the teacher, but also by the structure of the educational environment, relationships within the school, the expectations of society and the dynamics of academic relations. Each factor can lead to a systematic decrease in the teacher's emotional resources, intensification of stress in professional activity and, as a result, a deepening of the burnout process.

Social factors refer to the broader social and institutional environment in which a teacher operates and are among the most powerful influencing factors of burnout. The sharp increase in bureaucratic obligations, paperwork, electronic reports and inspections in the modern education system prevents teachers from devoting sufficient time to teaching, research and other academic activities, which increases the workload and creates the basis for emotional exhaustion. Low salaries and poor social security weaken teachers' work motivation, reduce their satisfaction with their professional activities and increase the risk of burnout by making them more vulnerable to daily stress.

Overcrowding of classes complicates pedagogical control, classroom management and individual approach, forcing the teacher to work under constant psychological stress. In modern times, the weakening of the teacher's authority in society compared to previous years is also an important social factor that contributes

to emotional burnout, because the level of value, support and respect given to the teacher's work seriously affects his internal motivation. In addition, high expectations from society for teachers - responsibility for the results of all students, control over behavior, the requirement to satisfy the wishes of parents - keep the teacher under constant psychological pressure. The presence of family and household stresses, economic difficulties and insufficient social support also weaken emotional resources and create an important social environment that accelerates burnout.

Psychological factors is related to the individual characteristics of the teacher and internal emotional regulation mechanisms and is considered the main intrapsychic factors in the development of burnout syndrome. Perfectionism, i.e. excessive demands on oneself, causes the teacher to try to perform every task ideally, and failure to meet these expectations in reality creates internal dissatisfaction and fatigue. Constant anxiety, self-criticism and negative self-esteem make the teacher more vulnerable to stress and facilitate burnout.

Poor stress management skills, difficulty in managing emotions, and ineffective problem-solving strategies keep teachers in a state of constant tension in the face of work pressure. Low self-esteem leads to subjective devaluation of professional achievements, feelings of incompetence, and loss of meaning in their activities. High emotional sensitivity, on the other hand, leads to a more acute reaction of teachers to the behavior of students, parents, and colleagues. Excessive empathy, on the other hand, leads to the loading of other people's problems onto the person's internal emotional system, which in the long run causes serious emotional exhaustion.

Socio-psychological factors determine the interaction between the social environment in which the teacher operates and his or her psychological state and constitutes one of the most critical areas of the burnout process. Conflicts with students, indiscipline in the teaching process, aggressive behavior and lack of motivation increase the emotional tension in the teacher and can gradually lead to depersonalization tendencies. Misunderstandings in parent-teacher relationships, excessive intervention or accusatory approach further aggravate the teacher's emotional burden.

Weak peer support, i.e. the lack of solidarity, cooperation and mutual assistance among teachers, creates a fertile psychological environment for burnout. Unhealthy principal-teacher relationships, unsupportive and critical approach of management cause teachers to feel unsafe. Lack of psychological safety in the work environment, i.e. the teacher's inability to freely express his/her opinions, fear of criticism and mobbing, constant tension and conflicts in the team further intensify emotional burnout.

Mobbing, intrigues, groupings, and negative relationships within the teaching staff disrupt the psychological climate and turn the work environment into a source of chronic stress. Each of these factors, complementing each other, can lead to the consistent depletion of a teacher's emotional resources, a decrease in motivation and productivity, and a more severe manifestation of burnout syndrome.

Preventing burnout in teachers requires a comprehensive approach, and in this process, strengthening individual resources, improving the social environment, and providing institutional support by educational institutions are of great importance. In order to effectively reduce burnout, it is necessary to apply preventive, psychological, and organizational interventions in parallel.

Individual (personal) strategies consists of personal measures that a teacher takes to protect his or her emotional resources and manage work stress. Improving stress management skills plays an important role in the prevention of emotional burnout. For this purpose, breathing techniques, relaxation exercises, meditation and muscle relaxation methods help restore teachers' psychological balance. Maintaining emotional boundaries is also of particular importance, since creating a balance between a teacher's personal and work life significantly reduces his or her risk of burnout. Time management skills, proper prioritization, workload planning and reduction of unnecessary tasks allow a teacher to manage his or her daily activities more effectively and stress-free.

Professional development strategies, i.e., attending trainings, learning new methods and innovative pedagogical approaches, increase the teacher's motivation and give him renewed energy in his work. Maintaining a healthy lifestyle - sufficient sleep, balanced nutrition, regular physical activity - reduces the physiological risks of emotional exhaustion and strengthens the overall psychophysiological state of the teacher.

Social strategies is aimed at strengthening the support received by the teacher from the environment and serves as an effective mechanism against burnout. Increased social support from family and close circle helps to reduce the emotional burden of the teacher, make him feel valued and understood. Joining professional communities - methodological associations and educational forums - allows teachers to exchange experiences, feel solidarity and prevent a sense of professional isolation.

Strengthening collegial cooperation, that is, effective communication with colleagues, joint activities, and strengthening support mechanisms, improves the psychological environment within the school and prevents teachers from struggling with stress alone.

Psychological intervention strategies. Psychological interventions include forms of professional support that are particularly effective in the deeper stages of emotional burnout. Psychological counseling and psychotherapeutic assistance allow the teacher to understand the causes of emotional burden, develop self-regulation skills, and restore internal resources. Diagnostics based on the Maslach Burnout Inventory objectively determine the level of burnout, allowing the psychologist to refine the intervention plan.

Stress management training introduces teachers to stress resilience strategies and provides practical skills. Emotional regulation and self-awareness programs help teachers better understand their emotions, express them in a healthy way, and maintain internal balance.

Cognitive-behavioral training helps teachers restructure negative automatic thoughts, correct irrational beliefs about work, and reduce emotional burden.

Organizational (institutional) interventions. Organizational interventions are systematic measures taken by educational institutions to improve teachers' working conditions and ensure their psychological well-being. Optimizing teachers' workload - reducing documentation requirements, balancing teaching hours and limiting additional tasks - significantly reduces the risk of burnout. Strengthening psychological service offices in educational institutions and implementing regular psychological prevention programs support the protection of teachers' emotional health.

Providing psychological safety in the work environment, that is, allowing teachers to freely express their opinions and be free from fear of criticism and mobbing, increases teacher motivation and job satisfaction. A supportive leadership model, empathetic and understanding management approaches help teachers feel valued and develop a positive attitude towards their professional activities. Expanding teachers' motivation systems - reward, appreciation mechanisms, career development opportunities - are important institutional tools that strengthen the protection of their emotional health and prevent burnout.

Conclusion

Emotional burnout syndrome is a significant psychological problem that limits the effective functioning of teachers in the modern education system. The essence of the syndrome is characterized by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and a decrease in the sense of personal achievement. Its physiological, psychological, and behavioral manifestations cover all aspects of pedagogical activity.

The development of burnout occurs in stages - from enthusiasm to apathy, and each stage requires careful observation. The social, psychological and socio-psychological factors that influence emotional burnout in teachers are complex. Therefore, it is important to apply intervention strategies at both the individual and organizational levels.

Scientifically based preventive measures not only improve the psychological well-being of teachers, but also improve the quality of the teaching process. When psychological health is considered a priority in the education system, the effects of emotional burnout are minimized and the continuity of teacher activity is ensured.

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